

Echoes of Inequality: Class and Caste Dynamics in Adiga's Portrait of Kittur

Anil Vandeo Andel¹ , Bhupendra Nandlal Kesur² *

Abstract

*The present paper explores the intricate dynamics of class and caste in Aravind Adiga's *Between the Assassinations*, focusing on the fictional town of Kittur as a microcosm of contemporary Indian society. Through a nuanced narrative structure that interweaves the stories of diverse characters, Adiga illustrates how systemic inequalities shape individual aspirations and experiences. The study situates caste as a pervasive barrier to social mobility, emphasizing its role as a mechanism of discrimination that perpetuates economic and social divides. The paper highlights the intersections of memory and trauma, demonstrating how historical injustices resonate through generations and inform the characters' realities. Additionally, it addresses the gendered dimensions of caste and class, showcasing how female characters navigate additional layers of oppression that complicate their social standing. The impact of globalization is also examined, revealing how the rise of a consumer culture in Kittur creates new class distinctions while exacerbating existing inequalities. Ultimately, this study underscores Adiga's narrative as both a reflection of societal realities and a call to confront the entrenched inequities that define life in India.*

Keywords: Inequality, caste, class, fictional town, gender, economic exploitation, migration, memory, globalization.

Introduction:

Aravind Adiga's *Between the Assassinations* offers a compelling exploration of contemporary Indian society, set against the backdrop of the fictional town of Kittur. In this intricate narrative, Adiga meticulously dissects the interplay of class and caste, revealing how these entrenched systems of inequality shape the lives of its inhabitants. Through a tapestry of interwoven stories, he highlights the multifaceted struggles of characters who navigate their aspirations

¹ Lecturer in English, Government Polytechnic Gondia, Maharashtra. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9908-8000>

^{2*} Professor and Head, Department of English, M.J. College, Jalgaon, Maharashtra. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5613-2198>

amidst the harsh realities of economic and social barriers. This examination is critical for understanding not only the individual experiences of Kittur's residents but also the broader implications of inequality in modern India. In *Between the Assassinations*, Kittur serves as a microcosm for examining these dynamics. The novel's structure allows for a nuanced exploration of how class and caste intersect to shape individual lives. Characters like the cart puller and other embody the aspirations and struggles of the lower classes, illustrating how economic desires clash with the realities of caste. Adiga poignantly encapsulates the omnipresent influence of class on personal ambition.

Moreover, Adiga deftly illustrates how caste operates as a formidable barrier to social mobility. Characters such as the Dalit labourer encounter systemic discrimination that confines them to the margins of society. This reflects Gupta's assertion that caste identities are often politicized, perpetuating entrenched inequalities (Gupta, 2005). The labourer's struggles are overshadowed by the ambitions of higher-caste individuals who exploit their labour, emphasizing the need to confront these structural injustices. The role of memory and trauma is also central to understanding the characters in Kittur. Adiga depicts how historical injustices resonate through generations, shaping present-day realities. The trauma of caste discrimination reverberates in the lives of Kittur's inhabitants, as illustrated by Cháirez-Garza's discussion on the spatial aspects of untouchability (Cháirez-Garza, 2022). Adiga poignantly conveys how deeply ingrained these hierarchies are in everyday life.

While the narrative predominantly focuses on male characters, female perspectives reveal the gendered dimensions of class and caste. Women in Kittur navigate additional layers of oppression, often constrained by both their gender and caste identities. An assistant headmaster exemplifies this complexity, as educational opportunities serve as both a pathway to empowerment and a reminder of the limitations imposed by social structures. This reflects the findings of Desai and Dubey who emphasize the intersectionality of gender, class, and caste in contemporary India (Desai & Dubey, 2011). Moreover, Adiga addresses the effects of globalization on local class structures, highlighting the emergence of new economic hierarchies. The influx of businesses and the rise of a service economy in Kittur create tensions between traditional values and modern aspirations. Appadurai's concept of "gastro-politics" illustrates how globalization commodifies local cultures, leading to hierarchical social orders based on economic power (Appadurai, 1981). This tension is evident in the characters' struggles for upward mobility, which are continually thwarted by their caste identities. *Between*

Received: 12 September 2024

Revised: 25 September 2024

Accepted: 5 October 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.13892646](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13892646)

the Assassinations serves as a poignant reflection on the echoes of inequality in contemporary Indian society. By examining class and caste dynamics through a multifaceted lens—drawing on Ambedkar’s theories and contemporary analyses—Adiga illuminates the persistent inequalities that define life in Kittur. His narrative is not merely a portrayal of social realities but a clarion call to recognize and confront the systemic injustices that continue to shape individual destinies in India today.

In analysing the class and caste dynamics depicted in Aravind Adiga’s *Between the Assassinations*, it is essential to ground the discussion in established theoretical frameworks. This analysis draws from several key theoretical perspectives, notably those articulated by B. R. Ambedkar, Pierre Bourdieu, and contemporary sociological insights on caste and class. This multidimensional framework allows for a nuanced exploration of how these systems of inequality manifest in the lives of the characters in Kittur.

Dr. Ambedkar’s Caste Theory

Central to this analysis is the theoretical framework established by Dr. B. R. Ambedkar, whose seminal works, particularly *Annihilation of Caste* (2011 [1936]) and *Who Were the Shudras* (2020 [1947]), provide vital insights into the oppressive structures of caste. Dr. Ambedkar argues that caste is a pervasive system of discrimination, necessitating dismantlement for the attainment of true equality. “The caste problem is a vast one, both theoretically and practically. Practically, it is an institution that portends tremendous consequences” (Ambedkar 1979, p. 5). Dr. Ambedkar’s critique of historical caste origins and their impact on social hierarchies informs understanding of Adiga’s characters, many of whom grapple with the legacies of caste discrimination that continue to limit their potential. Dr. Ambedkar further elucidates the socio-economic dimensions of caste, highlighting its implications for identity and power dynamics in modern India. By situating Adiga’s narrative within Dr. Ambedkar’s framework, it is observed how caste shapes the aspirations and limitations of characters, particularly those from marginalized communities.

Bourdieu’s Social Capital and Class Theory

Pierre Bourdieu’s concepts of social capital, cultural capital, and habitus are instrumental in understanding the class dynamics at play in Kittur. Bourdieu posits that social capital—the resources available to individuals through their social networks—significantly impacts their

life chances and opportunities. In the context of *Between the Assassinations*, the varying degrees of social capital possessed by characters illustrate the barriers to mobility created by class stratification. Adiga's characters exhibit different forms of cultural capital that reflect their education, social status, and exposure to broader cultural norms. For instance, the aspirations of a character from a lower caste may be thwarted by their limited access to educational resources, thereby reinforcing existing class disparities. By applying Bourdieu's framework, it is analysed how these intersecting forms of capital shape the characters' identities and experiences within the socio-economic landscape of Kittur.

Intersectionality and Gender

The intersectionality framework, developed by scholars like Kimberlé Crenshaw, emphasizes how overlapping identities—such as caste, class, and gender—create unique experiences of oppression and privilege. In *Between the Assassinations*, gendered dimensions of caste and class become apparent as female characters navigate additional layers of discrimination. This perspective allows for a deeper understanding of how women's experiences are shaped by both their caste identity and their social class. For instance, the struggles faced by female characters, such as those in traditional roles or in role as a professional, reflect the compounded effects of caste and gender. This intersectional approach highlights the unique challenges that arise from being both a woman and a member of a marginalized caste, as articulated by contemporary scholars like Chakravarti who examine the embodiment of caste in social interactions

Globalization and Class Dynamics

The framework of globalization offers further insights into the evolving class structures in Kittur. As Appadurai (1981) discusses in his examination of "gastro-politics," globalization transforms local economies and cultural practices, creating new forms of social stratification. In Adiga's narrative, the influx of businesses and the rise of a service economy introduce new class distinctions while exacerbating existing inequalities. Characters in Kittur navigate the tensions between traditional values and modern aspirations, illustrating how global economic changes impact local social hierarchies. By integrating globalization into the analysis, we can explore how Adiga critiques the commodification of culture and the implications of economic changes for social cohesion and identity.

Contemporary sociological research provides a backdrop for understanding the persistence of caste and class inequalities in modern India. Scholars such as Desai and Dubey (2011) highlight competing narratives around caste and its implications for social identity in the 21st century. This contemporary lens allows us to contextualize Adiga's work within ongoing debates about caste reform, identity politics, and social justice. Incorporating findings from recent studies on caste discrimination and the everyday experiences of caste, Guru and Sarukai further enrich our understanding of the lived realities faced by characters in *Between the Assassinations*. These insights illuminate how Adiga's portrayal resonates with current social issues, revealing the enduring legacy of caste and class in India.

By employing a multifaceted theoretical framework grounded in Ambedkar's caste theory, Bourdieu's social capital, intersectionality, globalization, and contemporary caste studies, it is gained comprehensive understanding of the class and caste dynamics in Adiga's *Between the Assassinations*. This analysis not only reveals the intricate layers of inequality within Kittur but also connects these themes to broader socio-political discourses in contemporary India. Ultimately, Adiga's work serves as a poignant reminder of the echoes of inequality that persist in society, inviting readers to reflect on the urgent need for social change.

Echoes of Inequality: Class and Caste Dynamics in *Between the Assassinations*

In Aravind Adiga's *Between the Assassinations*, the fictional town of Kittur serves as a microcosm for exploring the complex interplay between class and caste. Through a series of interconnected stories, Adiga reveals how these two systems of stratification shape the lives of the town's inhabitants, reflecting broader social realities in contemporary India. The caste system in Kittur is deeply entrenched, influencing the social fabric and everyday interactions among characters. For example, the plight of the Dalit characters is poignantly illustrated through the life of the man known as "Xerox" Ramkrishna who struggles against both economic and social barriers. The rich upper caste person comments upon Ramkrishna's profession of bookseller as:

That fucking son of an untouchable. See him snoring. "His father took out the shit—and this fellow thinks he's going to dump shit on us!" "Selling The Satanic Verses. He'll sell it under my nose, will he?" "These people think they

own India now. Don't they? They want all the jobs, and all the university degrees, and all the...(Adiga, 2015, p. 41)

This quote encapsulates the notion that caste identity severely limits individual potential and social mobility. Ramkrishna's despair reflects Dr. Ambedkar's assertion that caste is a systemic form of discrimination, rendering merit and effort irrelevant.

Adiga adeptly portrays the intersectionality of class and caste, demonstrating how these identities shape characters' aspirations and realities. The character of Shankara, who is always tortured by his low caste status. He searches for his identity despite his good economic background. He is indignant about caste system which torments lives of the people. He daringly confesses: "*I have burst a bomb to end the five-thousand-year-old caste system that still operates in our country. I have burst a bomb to show that no man should be judged, as I have been, merely by the accident of his birth*" (Adiga, 2015, p. 50-51). He is being humiliated due to his caste status. He is the son of Brahmin father and Hoyka (low caste) mother. Therefore, he cannot even mingle with Brahmin and Hoyka community due to his hybrid status of the Brahmo-Hoykas.

The novel also reveals how caste reinforces economic exploitation. For instance, the treatment of the Dalit characters by those from higher castes exemplifies systemic inequality. The wealthy landlords in Kittur exploit the labour of the lower castes, reinforcing both economic and social hierarchies. Chenayya, the cart puller always dreams of good life. He is too poor that he cannot have inhabitation. He defaecates in the open ground like stray animals. The example of Chenayya elucidates the economic exploitation at its apex. Despite his hard work, he remains confined by his low status, which determines his social standing in a city that thrives on economic mobility. Adiga pens, "The condition of the poor is becoming intolerable here." ... they lived in houses, they owned their vehicles. *You have to attain a certain level of richness before you can complain about being poor*" (Adiga, 2015, p.181). This line emphasizes that even within a bustling economic environment, the poor are deprived of aspirations, highlighting the profound impact of social stratification. The landlords saw the poor as mere tools, to be used and discarded as needed. This portrayal aligns with Bourdieu's concept of social capital, where those in power leverage their status to maintain control over marginalized groups.

Education is a recurring theme in the novel and serves as a critical factor in the quest for social mobility. However, access to education is often mediated by caste. Shankara is always humiliated by his classmates and teachers for his low caste status. He angrily shouts, “*No, you morons!* he wanted to shout. *It’s me! Shankara! The lower caste!*” (Adiga, 2015, p. 47) The character of Mr. D’Mello, assistant headmaster, would like to bring discipline in the lives of students. His efforts of imparting good education are always mocked by his colleagues. “Did the “reformer” not finally see the truth? Modern ideas of education were fine in Bangalore. But in a backwater like Kittur, miles and miles and miles away from civilization?” (Adiga, 2015, p. 82) Prevalent social norms and affinity to wrong things in society fall in the way of idealistic teacher. who ultimately meets with the death due to lewd propensity of his students.

Adiga’s portrayal of women in Kittur further complicates the narrative of class and caste. Female characters face unique challenges that intertwine with both caste and gender. For instance, the struggles of Shankara’s mother who is obvious in this manner. She is caught in between the low caste woman who is the wife of Brahmin. Shankara cannot understand her love for him too. She is afraid of her status. She does not want to face the Brahmin woman alone. She is only the wife and the mother. She is only accepted as the mother of male child-an heir. She always longs for acceptance and respectability. Even the higher caste woman cannot understand the situation of lower caste woman. Another character of Jayamma explores gender dimension of class and caste. Jayamma, a Brahmin cook, always faces misfortunes in the instalment. Though, she belongs to higher caste but devoid of affluence and luxury. She unwillingly works with Shaila, a girl from Hoyka caste. Jayamma, initially scorns the ways of Shaila, lower caste girl. Once, Jayamma thinks: “And all for what? Were the lower-castes meant to read and write?” (Adiga, 2015, p. 211-212) Jayamma holds responsible Shaila for the noise in house. She reports the master: “It’s not me making the noise, master—it’s that Hoyka girl! She doesn’t know our Brahmin ways” (Adiga, 2015, p. 212). But with the course of time, being a woman, she understands Shaila and treats her like a human being irrespective of Shaila’s low caste status.

Abbasi is concerned about the women who are working on dragon pattern of embroidery at his factory. Due to this work two women become blind. He shuts the factory. But when he reopens the factory, the other women come for embroidery work. “They knew their fate; but there was no other work to be had” (Adiga, 2015, p. 34). The women accept the situation to earn bread

and butter. They do not care about their health in the wake of financial problems. Another character, Ratnakar is worried about the marriage of his daughter. He has to manage amount to offer dowry to the would-be bride. The dominance of bride's family is evident in the novel. The family of girl are meant to be harassed by the family of boy under the sweet nomenclature of marriage. In the story, *Salt Market Village*, it is shown that how women are solely dependent on male in the male dominant society. In the absence of male in the family a widowed woman and her daughter named Sulochana have to seek shelter to politicians to get back their rights. Even an old man would like to marry Sulochana. "Now he was a dirty old man; he had become the stock figure whom he had worked into several of his stories—the lecherous old ... preying on an innocent girl of a lower caste" (Adiga, 2015, p. 308). This statement exhibits the severity in the low caste girls' life. Thus, it is highlighted how caste affects not only individual aspirations but also the dynamics within familial and social structures.

In *Between the Assassinations*, Aravind Adiga intricately weaves themes of memory and trauma into the fabric of Kittur, reflecting the profound impacts of caste and class dynamics on individual lives. Through the characters' recollections and experiences, Adiga illustrates how historical injustices, societal discrimination, and personal traumas resonate through the lives of Kittur's inhabitants, shaping their identities and interactions. Memory plays a critical role in understanding the trauma experienced by characters from marginalized backgrounds. The recollections of Shankara are fraught with pain and suffering stemming from both personal and communal histories of oppression. Every time he closes his eyes, he is reminded of the beatings, the insults, the endless cycle of degradation. Adiga writes, "He kneeled with his eyes to the ground, and thought, over and over again, *He is doing this to me because I am a Hoyka. If I were a Christian or a Bunt he would never have humiliated me like this.*" (Adiga, 2015, p. 55). This vivid imagery highlights how memories are not just personal but are collective echoes of a caste-based trauma that extends beyond individual experiences. Once, a Brahmin boy in school invites him home. He takes a chance and visits boy's home. The boy and his mother invites Shankara into the drawing room. It is a "modern" family—they have lived abroad. He sees miniature Eiffel Towers and porcelain milkmaids in the drawing room, and he feels reassured that he would not be ill-treated there. He is given tea and biscuits, and made to feel perfectly at home. But as he leaves, he turns and sees his friend's mother with a cleaning rag in her left hand. She had begun wiping the sofa where he has been sitting. Ramkrishna is beaten in the police station by the upper caste inspector and lawyer under the influence of liquor.

Received: 12 September 2024

Revised: 25 September 2024

Accepted: 5 October 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.13892646](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13892646)

Ramkrishna's knee is broken due to his daring to become book seller irrespective of his low caste status. He feels broken for the incident. The trauma harasses him in a such extent that he determines to sell banned copies of *Satanic Verses* despite its banned. The burden of memory in this context aligns with Ambedkar's observations on the psychological impact of caste, where historical injustices are carried forward through generations, perpetuating cycles of trauma and victimhood. (Ambedkar, 2011, p. 23). The characters' memories become a lens through which we understand the pervasive nature of caste oppression in Kittur.

Adiga also emphasizes the importance of collective memory in shaping the identity of Kittur. The town's history is fraught with caste conflicts, communal tensions, and socio-economic disparities that resonate throughout the narrative. This portrayal of Kittur as a living entity, steeped in collective memory, underscores how the past continues to influence the present. The concept of collective memory is essential in understanding how societal attitudes toward caste and class are maintained and challenged. The memories of the past are not merely personal; they shape the community's identity and inform its ongoing struggles for justice and equality.

In *Between the Assassinations*, Aravind Adiga explores the effects of globalization on class dynamics within the fictional town of Kittur. As India undergoes rapid economic changes, the impact of globalization is felt in various aspects of life, reshaping social structures, economic opportunities, and class relations. Globalization introduces a new economic landscape in Kittur, characterized by the growth of industries and the influx of capital. This economic shift creates opportunities for some but exacerbates inequalities for others. Adiga depicts Kittur is changing, with new shops and factories sprouting like weeds, but the old caste lines were drawn deeper. This statement captures the dual nature of globalization: while it fosters economic growth, it also reinforces existing social divisions rooted in caste. The introduction of modern industries leads to a transformation in labour dynamics. Higher-caste individuals often take advantage of new business opportunities, while lower-caste workers remain relegated to low-paying, menial jobs. The character of Chenayya embodies this tension, as he grapples with the desire for upward mobility amid persistent barriers. He sees the wealth around him but felt the invisible wall that kept him on the other side. He plans to steal money to live comfortable life. But he soon realises that he would be caught in doing so. He thinks: "*Somewhere, I hope, a poor man will strike a blow against the world. Because there is no God watching over us. There is no one coming to release us from the jail in which we have locked ourselves*" (Adiga, 2015, p.187). It highlights the ways in which globalization can create wealth while simultaneously entrenching

Received: 12 September 2024

Revised: 25 September 2024

Accepted: 5 October 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.13892646](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13892646)

class and caste divisions. Globalization also brings about a consumer culture that influences class dynamics in Kittur. As new products and lifestyles become available, the desire for material goods creates a competitive environment among different social strata. Adiga points out the consumerism of the rich. The rich people afford to waste their money on the products which cost less at another places.

“I’m telling you about the rich. In Bombay, at the Oberoi Hotel in Nariman Point, there is a dish called Beef Vindaloo that costs five hundred rupees.” ... Now you know about the rich.” “What if you order the dish, and then you realize you made a mistake and you don’t like it? Do you get your money back?” “No, but it doesn’t matter to you if you’re rich. You know what the biggest difference is between being rich and being like us? The rich can make mistakes again and again. We make only one mistake, and that’s it for us.” (Adiga, 2015, p. 231)

Globalization fosters migration, as individuals seek better economic opportunities beyond Kittur. Adiga portrays the experiences of migrant workers who leave for cities or abroad in search of work. The character of the young man who migrates reflects the hope and desperation that drive such decisions. The large number of migrant workers in Kittur are usually working on construction site. Adiga portrays: “an army of bare-chested migrant workers carrying stacks of bricks and cement bags on their heads like ants moving grains of rice” (Adiga, 2015, p. 286). These are mostly Tamil-speaking migrants from nearby towns. Few of them are working as cleaner. They are cleaning gutter situated in the posh area of the rich in order to earn bread and butter for the family. Keshava, the migrant dreams for a job of reputation. But ultimately defeated by his fate. Population and migration are interlinked to each other. Thimma understands about the situation of Ziauddin, “Thimma learned that the whippersnapper was nearly twelve. He was the sixth of eleven children from a farm-laboring family up in the north of the state” (Adiga, 2015, p. 4). Being a migrant, Ziauddin suffers his lot in Kittur. Even in new environments, caste and class distinctions persist. This highlights the enduring nature of caste identities, suggesting that globalization does not erase these barriers but rather complicates them.

Globalization has introduced itself the amelioration of thinking in respect of caste and class equality in the contemporary India. The stubborn people of old mentality are not ready to accept the changes in the contemporary society and they are still glued with their traditional pride of

caste and class. Adiga depicts: “And here you are talking of bikinis and wikinis, and cavorting with ‘modern’ people, instead of praying to God to forgive your sins!” (Adiga, 2015, p.283) The people who deny the change, deny the way of life of other for their personal void pride and gain. But there are people who are also accepting the change in society. Adiga hints the receding effect of caste in the age of globalization in the statement: “Today, there is no such thing as caste,” the man said with regret. “Brahmins eat meat. Kshatriyas get educated and write books. And lower castes convert to Christianity and Islam...” (Adiga, 2015, p. 59). It is the matter of assimilation of wider outlook in the way thinking of ours to accept the identity of other living being. The awareness about others’ rights and independence is the key factor to impart positive change in society. Therefore, Adiga underlines: “The old, bad India of caste and class privilege—the India of child marriage, of ill-treated widows, of exploited subalterns—it had to be overthrown” (Adiga, 2015, p. 301).

Conclusion

In *Between the Assassinations*, Aravind Adiga masterfully illuminates the intricate web of class and caste dynamics that pervade the fictional town of Kittur, offering a profound commentary on the persistent inequalities that characterize contemporary Indian society. By employing a narrative structure that intertwines the lives of diverse characters, Adiga not only portrays their individual struggles but also reveals how systemic structures shape their destinies. The characters’ experiences reflect a microcosm of larger societal issues, echoing the insights of Dr. B. R. Ambedkar, whose critiques of caste as a mechanism of discrimination continue to resonate powerfully today. Through the lens of Dr. Ambedkar’s theories, we understand that caste is not merely a relic of the past but a living force that impacts social mobility and personal aspirations. The systemic barriers faced by the characters underscore the ongoing relevance of Ambedkar’s call for dismantling these oppressive structures. Kittur is the town where aspirations of the poor are often stifled by entrenched hierarchies. It also reveals the intersectionality of caste and politics, revealing how power dynamics perpetuate economic and social inequalities. Adiga poignantly illustrates how injustices manifest in everyday life, shaping not only individual identities but also the physical spaces they inhabit. Adiga also highlights the gendered dimensions of class and caste, emphasizing how women navigate additional layers of oppression. This intersectionality reflects broader social dynamics, resonating with contemporary discussions on gender and caste. Moreover, the impact of

globalization introduces new dimensions to the class dynamics in Kittur. The influx of businesses and the rise of a consumer culture create both opportunities and tensions, revealing how traditional values are often at odds with modern aspirations. Characters striving for upward mobility find themselves caught in a paradox where economic advancement remains inextricably linked to their caste or class identities. Adiga's exploration of these themes serves as a crucial reminder of the complexities that arise when global influences collide with local realities. Adiga's *Between the Assassinations* serves as a poignant and urgent reflection on the echoes of inequality that continue to shape the lives of individuals in India. By dissecting the interconnections of class and caste through a multifaceted narrative, Adiga not only captures the harsh realities faced by his characters but also challenges readers to confront the systemic injustices that persist in society. This call to awareness and action is vital in the ongoing struggle for equality, inviting us to recognize and dismantle the barriers that continue to define the human experience in Kittur and beyond.

References

- Adiga, Aravind. (2015). *Between the Assassinations*. Picador India, an imprint of Pan Macmillan India.
- Ambedkar, B. R. (2011). *Annihilation of Caste*. Prabuddha Bhart Pustkalya. (Original work published 1936)
- Ambedkar, B. R. (1979). *Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar: Writings and Speeches* (Vol. 1). Dr. Ambedkar Foundation, Ministry of Social Justice & Empowerment, Govt. of India.
- Ambedkar, B. R. (2020). Who were the Shudras. In *Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar: Writings and Speeches* (Vol. 7). Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment. (Original work published 1947)
- Appadurai, Arjun. (1981). Gastro-politics in Hindu South Asia. *American Ethnologist*, 8(3), 494–511. <https://doi.org/10.1525/ae.1981.8.3.02a00020>
- Bourdieu, Pierre. (1977). *Outline of a Theory of Practice* (R. Nice, Trans.). Cambridge University Press. (Original work published 1972)
- Bourdieu, Pierre. (1984). *Distinction: A social Critique of the Judgement of Taste*. Routledge.
- Bourdieu, Pierre. (1994). *Language and Symbolic Power* (J. B. Thompson, Ed.). Harvard University Press.
- Carswell, Grace, De Neve, Geert, & Heyer, J. (2017). Caste discrimination in contemporary Tamil Nadu: Evidence from the Tiruppur textile region. In *Social Inequalities in India* (pp. 134–156). University of Sussex. <https://hdl.handle.net/10779/uos.23441957.v1>

Cháirez-Garza, Jorge. (2022). Moving untouched: B. R. Ambedkar and the Racialization of Untouchability. *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 45(2), 216–234.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/01419870.2022.2030778>

Chakravarti, Uma. (2003). *Gendering Caste: Through a Feminist Lens*. Stree.

Crenshaw, Kimberlé. (1989). Demarginalizing the Intersection of Race and Sex: A Black Feminist Critique of Antidiscrimination Doctrine, Feminist Theory, and Antiracist Politics. *University of Chicago Legal Forum*, 1989(1), 139–167.

<https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1018799>

Desai, Sonalde, & Dubey, Amaresh. (2011). Caste in 21st century India: Competing Narratives. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 46(11), 40–49.

Gorringe, Hugo, & Rafanell, Iñaki. (2007). Caste, Class and Gender: A New Perspective on Social Inequalities in Contemporary India. In *Social Inequalities in India* (pp. 49–72). Sage Publications.

Guru, Gopal, & Sarukai, Suryakant. (2019). *Experience, Caste and Everyday Social*. Oxford University Press.

Gupta, Dipankar. (2005). Caste and Politics: Identity over System. *Annual Review of Anthropology*, 21, 409–427.

<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.anthro.21.090503.090337>